

The Effect of Subjective Norm and Perceived Risk on Consumers' Purchase Intention towards Secondhand Clothes

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ABSTRACT: Fashion serves as a form of self-expression and symbolizes various social, cultural, and economic statuses. The rise of affordable and accessible fashion has led to significant environmental concerns due to increased textile waste. Due to these emerging issues, the slow fashion movement has been gaining popularity with the sustainable and ethical value it brings to the table, particularly through social media platforms that foster communities advocating for eco-conscious fashion choices. With slow fashion being a relatively new topic, challenges are faced that withholds the growth of slow fashion in Indonesia. Hence, this research was conducted to explore consumers' perception and intention towards slow fashion products along with the factors affecting it. From the objective of the research, variables were identified and hypotheses were constructed to explain the relationship between each variable. In order to fulfill the objectives of the research, a quantitative research approach was obtained to gather various and in-depth information regarding the topic. The quantitative approach was obtained through mini surveys utilizing online questionnaires and the result was processed through the PLS-SEM method using SmartPLS software, where the result was explained through descriptive analysis, validity and reliability testing, hypothesis testing, and suitability evaluation and goodness of fit model testing. The result found that subjective norms have a positive impact on consumers' purchase intention towards the products, whereas perceived risk negatively affects the intention to purchase slow fashion products. Suggestions were also provided for many parties to ensure the development of the slow fashion movement in the future.

KEYWORDS: Purchase Intention, Perceived Risk, Slow Fashion, Subjective Norm.

INTRODUCTION

Fashion has evolved into a means of personal expression and a reflection of cultural, social, and economic status (Trisnawati, 2011). The widespread availability of affordable fashion has enabled people from various income levels to express themselves through clothing (Sabilla et al., 2023). However, this rise in fashion consumption has led to increased textile waste, with the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency reporting that nearly 65% of textile waste ends up in landfills (2020). The growth of fast fashion, driven by young female consumers, has further exacerbated this issue (Cavender & Lee, 2018).

In response to the environmental impact of fast fashion, the slow fashion movement has emerged, promoting sustainable and ethical practices in fashion. Slow fashion advocates for responsible sourcing, production, and consumption, offering longer-lasting garments that are less damaging to the environment and provide fair wages to laborers (Brewer, 2019). Social media has played a significant role in spreading awareness about slow fashion, with communities on platforms like Instagram and TikTok advocating for more sustainable fashion choices (Nti, 2019). An easy way to comply with the conference paper formatting requirements is to use this document as a template and simply type your text into it. Wherever Times is specified, Times Roman or Times New Roman may be used.

The slow fashion conversation has gained traction in Indonesia, especially since the Slow Fashion Lab exhibition in 2017 (Nti, 2019). Despite increased awareness, the adoption of slow fashion faces challenges due to consumer behavior and market adaptation. The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) suggest that societal norms and product knowledge influence consumer purchase intentions, which creates challenges for the newly-introduced concept like slow fashion (Perdanawati et al., 2020). Consumers' perceived risk towards new topic is also capable to withhold consumers' intention to purchase slow fashion products, which can be explained by the Theory of Perceived Risk (Li & Huang, 2009).

Nevertheless, slow fashion has potential in Indonesia, with pioneering brands like Sejauh Mata Memandang inspiring sustainable practices (Mulyaningsih & Tobing, 2023). Social media influencers promoting slow fashion and secondhand clothing

have further raised awareness. Slow fashion brands are still slowly emerging in Indonesia, which needs to be analysed in hopes to quicken the greater impact of slow fashion movement. Understanding consumer behavior, particularly subjective norms and perceived risks, is essential for the growth of slow fashion movement in Indonesia.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design to thoroughly investigate consumer perceptions and intentions regarding slow fashion, utilizing data from respondents.

Research Data Collection Technique, Population, & Sample

An online mini-survey will collect quantitative data, which will be transformed into statistical formats for analysis, examining each variable to understand their relationships. The study's population includes Indonesians aged 17-54 who have bought or used secondhand fashion products, with a minimum sample size of 200, collected through social media and word-of-mouth (Malhotra, 2016). Purposive sampling will be used to target specific respondents, optimizing resources and ensuring focused data collection (Campbell et al., 2020; Andrade, 2020). Data analysis will be conducted using SmartPLS 4 software for partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to provide statistical insights and validate the data (Sarstedt & Cheah, 2019).

Operational Definition of Variables

- 1. Subjective Norm:** An individual's thinking and behavior are influenced by subjective norms, which refer to the perceived expectations and opinions of others about engaging in specific behaviors (Septifani et al., 2014)
- 2. Perceived Risk:** Unintended consequences to avoid in purchasing decisions (Peter & Olson, 2012)
- 3. Purchase Intention:** Intention, influenced by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, affects consumers' final purchasing behavior (Dakduk et al., 2017).

Hypotheses Development

1. Subjective Norm and Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) suggest that subjective norms influence an individual's intention and behavior (Dakduk et al., 2017). Studies have shown that subjective norms positively impact consumer behavior, such as pre-purchase behavior for sustainable clothing consumption (Rausch & Kopplin, 2021). This research will examine the buying intention of used/secondhand clothes in Indonesia to understand consumer interest in the slow fashion movement.

H1: Subjective Norm has a significant influence on Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes

2. Perceived Risk and Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes

Perceived risk arises among consumers as they try to avoid unforeseen consequences of their purchases (Peter & Olson, 2012). Studies show high perceived risk can lower purchase intention (Kurniawan et al., 2023; Rebecca, 2023). This research will examine whether perceived risk negatively affects consumers' purchasing intentions towards secondhand clothes, a key aspect of the slow fashion movement.

H2: Perceived Risk has a significant influence on Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Demographic Profile

The data on slow fashion product users shows that the majority are aged 17 to 25 years old (60.6%). Gender distribution reveals that females dominate the slow fashion industry. Geographically, most slow fashion users are concentrated in Java, followed by Sumatera, Kalimantan, Bali & Nusa Tenggara, Sulawesi, and Papua Maluku. Regarding monthly expenses, 40.3% of respondents spend between Rp1,000,000 and Rp2,500,000, while 33.3% spend between Rp2,500,000 and Rp5,000,000.

Data Analysis Result

The data has surpassed the validity and reliability test, which includes outer loadings test, construct reliability and validity test, discriminant validity test, and variance inflation factors. The data analysis result shows as follows.

Hypothesis	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	T-statistics	P-values	R-Square	Result
H1	Subjective Norm	Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes	12.295	0.00	0.52	Accepted
H2	Perceived Risk		7.299	0.00		Accepted

Both hypotheses are accepted: subjective norms positively influence purchase intention towards slow fashion products, while perceived risk negatively affects it. This is supported by meeting T-statistics and P-value thresholds, and confirmed by validity and reliability tests. The R-Square value shows a moderate influence of these variables on purchase intention towards slow fashion.

H1: Subjective Norm (SN) positively influences Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes (PISC)

The first hypothesis is confirmed, showing that subjective norms positively influence consumers' intention to purchase slow fashion products, with a highly significant T-statistic value of 12.295, well above the threshold. The most influential indicator is SN1, highlighting that peer influence is crucial in driving consumers to buy secondhand clothes. This supports Ajzen & Fishbein's Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), emphasizing that social norms are key to understanding and predicting consumer behavior toward slow fashion. The findings align with previous research showing that subjective norms promote sustainable clothing consumption (Rausch & Kopplin, 2021), suggesting that increasing awareness of slow fashion within social circles can enhance its adoption and positively impact the fashion industry.

H2: Perceived Risk (PR) negatively influences Purchase Intention Towards Secondhand Clothes (PISC)

The second hypothesis, which states that perceived risk negatively affects consumers' intention to purchase slow fashion products, is supported by the results. The T-statistic value of 7.299 indicates a significant negative relationship, with concerns about product quality being the most prominent risk factor. This suggests that perceived risks, such as doubts about the quality of secondhand clothes, deter consumers from buying slow fashion products. Highlighting the quality of these garments and increasing public awareness about slow fashion can mitigate misconceptions and encourage more eco-conscious purchasing decisions (Koay et al., 2022).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Conclusion

Subjective norms significantly influence consumers' intention to buy secondhand clothes, as societal perspectives—whether positive or negative—shape consumer attitudes toward slow fashion. Positive perceptions in the environment enhance purchase intentions, highlighting the need for spreading accurate and favorable information about slow fashion. Furthermore, consumers' perceived risk, particularly concerns about hygiene and product quality, negatively impacts their intention to purchase secondhand clothes. Addressing and debunking these misconceptions is crucial to increasing consumer interest in slow fashion. Lastly, consumers generally show interest in slow fashion products due to positive experiences, high-quality garments, unique designs, and lower prices. However, issues such as sanitary concerns and unfamiliarity with thrifting still affect some consumers' willingness to buy. This presents an opportunity for the slow fashion industry to address these concerns and further promote its benefits.

Recommendation

For slow fashion business practitioners, the research provides valuable insights for developing effective marketing strategies, emphasizing the importance of targeting young adults who show greater interest in slow fashion. To attract consumers, businesses should highlight the unique benefits of slow fashion, utilize referral discounts, and collaborate with influencers, leveraging the positive impact of subjective norms on purchase intention. Ensuring high product quality and addressing perceived risks through transparency, customer reviews, and return policies will also help boost consumer confidence and interest. Consumers are encouraged to educate themselves about the

environmental impact of fast fashion, care for their current clothing, and choose high-quality, durable items. Sharing positive experiences with slow fashion and participating in community initiatives can further promote sustainable consumption. Future research should explore why young adults are particularly interested in slow fashion, investigate other demographic segments, and examine additional factors like income and social media exposure that might influence purchasing intentions.

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